

Impact of climate change on the *Kuakata* sea shore of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study aims to assess the diversity of flora and fauna on the shore of *Kuakata* of Bangladesh and examine the probable impact of climate change. Both primary and secondary data were used to identify the plants and animals and to predict future changes in the ecosystem. It was found that there are uneven and mixed patches of trees dominated by *Keora* (*Sonneratia apetala*) and *Gewa* (*Excoecaria agallocha*) in the *Fatra* and *Gangamati* mangrove forests. The pioneer species *Sundari* (*Heritiera fomes*) trees are occasionally distributed in these forests. *Golpata* (*Nypa fruticans*) and *Hantol* (*Phoenix paludosa*) are the indicator plant species of these ecosystems. *Kakra* (*Bruguiera gymnorhiza*) and *Pashur* (*Xylocarpus mekongensis*) have become rare species though they were abundant a few decades back. Sporadic patches of *Hogla* (*Typha elephantina*) and *Golpata* exist throughout the area. The plant species composition differs greatly within the forests and the canopy closure is a mosaic. It was found that tropical cyclone *Aila* caused mass devastation, altered vegetation composition and facilitated biological invasion. The climatic factors include sedimentations, inundation stress and increased salinity at landward zones. The study recommended several mitigation measures to overcome the challenges.

Keywords: *Kuakata*, Climate change, tropical cyclone, *Aila*, *Fatra* and *Gangamati* mangroves, mitigation

Introduction

Kuakata, locally known as *Sagar Kannya* (daughter of the sea) is located in the southwest of Bangladesh. Next to *Cox's Bazar*, it is the second most famous sea beach in this country. And *Kuakata* is one of the rarest sea beaches in the world, which has a rare scenic beauty offering the full view of the rising and setting of the crimson sun in the water of the Bay of Bengal. This 30 km long and 03 km wide beach has a typical natural setting and is sandy as gently slopes into the Bay of Bengal.

It is 70 km away from *Patuakhali* district headquarters and 320 km from the capital Dhaka. The site is characterised by an excellent combination of eye-catching natural beauty, sandy beach, blue sky, a huge expanse of water of the Bay and evergreen forest. The unique customs of the '*Rakhine*' tribal families and the Buddhist temple of about a hundred years old indicate the ancient tradition and cultural heritage in the area.

Kuakata is a unique example of the co-occurrence of different ecosystems. There are remnants of mangroves on this beach. The line of coconut trees has increased the scenic beauty of this seashore. The nearby *Fatra* and *Gangamati* mangrove forests (part of Sundarbans) have enriched the biodiversity of this territory. The tamarisk (*Jhau*) forests have added more attraction to this beach.

There are uneven and mixed patches of trees dominated by *Keora* (*Sonneratia apetala*) and *Gewa* (*Excoecaria agallocha*). The pioneer species *Shundari* (*Heritiera fomes*) trees are occasionally distributed in these forests. *Golpata* (*Nypa fruticans*) and *Hantol* (*Phoenix paludosa*) are the indicator plant species of these ecosystems. *Kakra* (*Bruguiera gymnorhiza*) and *Pashur* (*Xylocarpus mekongensis*) have become rare species though they were abundant a few decades back. Sporadic patches of *Hogla* (*Typha elephantina*) and *Golpata* exist throughout the area. The plant species composition differs greatly within the forests and the canopy closure is a mosaic.

The forests are characterized by several small patches of mature trees, shrublands, isolated old trees and denuded sands. These forests are habitats of the rhesus monkey, wild boar, spotted deer, snakes, forest owl, fox, wildfowl and lizards. Mangroves as well as the beach are the home to turtles, molluscs, crabs, seaweeds and sea birds, and provide excellent nurseries for marine fishes

like *Hilsha*, Hamilton (*Baila*), Asian Sea Bass (*Koral*), Black Sea Bass (*Bhol Koral*), Silver Pomfret (*Ruupchanda*), dolphins and shrimps.

Kuakata is a virgin abode of migratory winter birds. It is the home of the Cotton Pygmy-goose, White-winged duck, Sarus crane, Eurasian Thick-knee, Indian Cormorant, White-bellied heron, Pacific Reef Egret, Malayan Night-heron, Glossy Ibis, Woolly-necked stork, Asian Openbill, Indian Pond heron, Black-bellied Tern, Gull-billed Tern, Spot-billed duck, Lesser Whistling-duck, Watercock, etc. Migratory birds like Common Shelduck, Ruddy Turnstone, Sanderling, Great Knot, Long-billed Ringed Plover, Crab Plover, Caspian Tern, Spot-billed Pelican, White Stork, etc. come in winter from the temperate regions.

The environmental parameters with the direct influences on this island in terms of global climate change are sea-level rise, natural calamities like cyclones, and rise in temperature and salinity. Bangladesh faces unpredictable climate change impacts for a long that is subject to multiple stressors originating from a rapidly changing environment (Rahman 2020, Rahman 2021a, Rahman 2022c, Rahman 2023b, c, d, e, f, g) and social dynamics (Mitchell et al.2015, Rahman *et al.* 2009, Rahman 2021b, Rahman 2022a, b). The study also predicted the upcoming impact of climate change on the ecosystem.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from Forest Department. Local people were personally interviewed to identify the flora and fauna. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to understand the future projections and mitigation strategy. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Responses of Biodiversity to climatic stressors

The respondents opined that climate change has already affected the coastal ecosystems of the northern hemisphere. This is also a region of transition between the freshwater of the rivers (*Payra*, *Bishkhali* and *Agunmukha*) and the saline water of the Bay of Bengal. The luxuriant biodiversity of the *Kuakata* region has strong interactions with the marine environment. The environmental parameters with the direct influences on mangroves (*Fatra* and *Gangamati* forests), Coconut orchards, *Jhau Bans* and the beach in terms of global climate change are sea-

level rise, cyclones, rise in temperature and salinity. The species composition of *Fatra* and *Gangamati* forests may undergo a major change, depending on the severity of the predicted climate change impact.

Sea level rise, increased salinity and inundation will change the forest's nature. A one-metre rise in sea level will destroy the whole ecosystem. Shrubland and dune vegetation will be submerged. The occasionally distributed pioneer species *Sundari* will be replaced by *Keora* and *Gewa*. The mixed stands will be converted into pure stands and old-grown forests will be changed into new successional forests. *Sundari*, *Kakra* and *Pashur* will be highly vulnerable even in low-level sea rise (8-9cm/100 years) while they will be extinct from these ecosystems in medium-level sea rise (9-12cm/100 years). *Keora* and *Gewa* will be able to keep pace with low-level sea rise. In high-level sea rise (>9-12cm/100 years) all existing plant species will be lost except aquatic plants. The repetition of cyclones like *Sidr* and *Aila* will degrade the habitats and the affected forests will be unsuitable for natural regeneration. Sediments carried by storm surges will cause plant mortality by interfering with root and soil gas exchange. Alien exotic plant species will be rapidly suppressing native flora.

Coconut palms will be highly affected by high temperatures. Pollen viability will be reduced with the increase in temperature affecting reproductive development. Deformation of fruits will occur resulting in a small number of nuts, empty nuts or elongated nuts. Predicted climate change will be congenial for *Jhau* but the introduction of invasive species may cause local decline and even extinction of tamarisk. Invasive species will change community composition and ecosystem functioning.

The monkey, spotted deer, wild boar, fox and lizards will face a shortage of food. They, often in groups will move to the locality by swimming in rivers and canals for foraging foods and sweet water. Many of them will die of drowning or being caught by crocodiles and people.

Most of the fish species and shrimps utilize fresh water for spawning and juvenile feeding. The Hilsa needs sweet water to lay their eggs and the hatchlings move towards marine water where they attain adulthood. The breeding habitat of most of the fish species and other crustaceans will be destroyed by the intrusion of salinity. The migration of certain fish species out of their natural habitats will cause food shortages for thousands of people.

Forty per cent of the algae population may die due to climate change by the end of this century (Rahman 2023a). Sea-level rise will cause erosion of turtle nesting beaches. The higher sand temperature will lead to changes in sex ratios or prevent eggs from hatching. Huge rainfall may raise groundwater tables, thereby flooding the nests of turtles. Sea acidification will decline the abundance of the mollusc. The breeding place of crabs and shrimps will be destroyed due to sea level rise.

The plant parts of *Fatra* and *Gangamati* mangrove vegetation provide nourishment for young fish, shrimps, and crabs. In the changed environment, only a handful would survive. Mangrove trees also provide habitats to young fish, shrimps, crabs and molluscs. The mangrove trees provide not only support to countless food webs; they are also indirectly responsible for the survival of the most primary planktonic and epiphytic algal food chains. High salt concentration will make the ecosystem unfavourable for most of the species.

Ground birds will be severely affected by losing their habitats, nesting and breeding sites. The high sea temperature will affect seabirds' foraging success, growth patterns and reproductive potentiality. Global warming will affect the abundance and spatial distribution of birds. Cyclones will cause large-scale mortality of adults, exposure of eggs and young, starvation or structural failure of nests. Climate change will affect the abundance and availability of food (i.e., arthropods) which influences nestling survival and the frequency of double-brooding and hence seasonal fecundity.

How to mitigate?

- * Monitoring of biological resources and the impact of climate change to adopt appropriate biodiversity management
- * Emphasising an adaptive or community-based conservation programme
- * Combining adaptation and mitigation measures
- * Planned adaptation options to climate change will consider three approaches namely planned retreat, accommodation, and protection
- * Developing alternative livelihoods for the fishermen
- * Initiating conservation programme for the migratory birds

- * Declaring the *Fatra* and *Gangamati* mangroves as natural forest reserves
- * Protecting natural regeneration to promote natural succession in the denuded lands of *Fatra* and *Gangamati* mangroves
- * Creating public awareness
- * Strengthening research work on the impact of climate change
- * Emphasising ex-situ conservation of occasional and rare species like *Sundari*, *Pashur* and *Kakra*
- * Establishing an information system of biodiversity
- * Raising funds for the conservation programme
- * Restoring and maintaining mangroves to minimise erosion
- * Designing and establishing a sea-level/climate modelling network
- * Establishing database systems for biological resources
- * Integrated coastal and marine management
- * Assessing coastal vulnerability and risk to climate change
- * Increasing waterfront setbacks in beachfront areas
- * Education on climate change and emergency preparedness at all levels
- * Developing coastal infrastructure
- * Protecting existing mangroves against encroachment and cutting
- * Afforestation and reforestation by salt-tolerant species like *Gewa* and *Keora*
- * Establishing mechanisms to promote carbon uptake
- * Digging out thickets of invasive plant species from the *Jhau* forests
- * Gap-filling by native species in the *Jhau* forests and mangroves to protect against invasion by exotic species

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